

DESCRIPTION OF REALIS/IRREALIS AND MODALITY CATEGORIES

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Abstract. *This article dwells on an analysis of the phenomenon realis/irrealis and its reflection on the language, as well as an analysis of the modality category in the English language.*

Keywords: *epistemic modality, indicative, subjective, realis/irrealis, grammatical expression.*

Until now, in the typological studies of irrealis, as well as in the analysis of individual languages, the consideration of epistemic modality as an irrealis phenomenon is rarely noticeable. In these studies, concepts that have some meaning of potential or possibility close to epistemological modality are defined as irrealis. But the words used by the speaker are rarely marked as irrealis.

For example, B. Palmer states that realis/irrealis is equivalent to indicative/subjective, while J. Elliot believes that realis should be distinguished from tendency and modality. In addition, it is not clear that the definitions of realities are always applied to the same extent. For example, J. Elliot makes the following points about the “concepts of realis/irrealis”:

a) the realist confirms that the event or situation is activated as a prototype or that they are based on a concrete fact;

b) irrealis prototypically means that the event is imaginary or hypothetical, and therefore represents a potential or possible event, but does not represent the observable reality of realis.

It is not clear why J. Elliot defines realis as “affirming” and irrealis as “considering”, but later he replaces the word “event” with “event or condition”. For example:

Realis status can be understood as a grammatical expression of an event or situation occurring in real reality or some hypothetical reality. Similarly, B. Palmer begins his definition by noting that modality (which he defines as realis/irrealis, as mentioned above) “is related to the status of the sentence describing its phenomenon.” But later he comments that there is a difference between “proposal modality” and “event modality”. This probably means that some types of modality/realis markers do not fit the previous definition semantically.

It becomes clear that J. Bybee’s proposal to evaluate irrealis and modality in the same category cannot be a solution to all problems related to the concept of irrealis. Indeed, despite the fact that modality and irrealis are close to each other in many literatures, it is emphasized that there are some fundamental differences between them, regardless of the definition of modality. It should be noted that the category of modality is evaluated by the presence of properties such as agent-oriented, speaker-oriented, epistemic and subordinate.

As D. Winford points out, in fact, a modalized sentence is always expressed by an epistemic and speaker-oriented modality, but because it is an agent, it is subject to temporal changes. This comparison shows that the modal sentence is interpreted as an agent-directed attitude. However, in modal sentences directed to the agent expressed in the past tense, it can be interpreted as activated.

In another definition, modality is determined by the grammaticalization of the speaker's subjective attitude towards the topic or concept he is talking about. This narrow definition excludes agent-based modality.

This narrow meaning of modality does not describe subjective relations, but actually situational, objective, neutral states of necessity or possibility. Thus, according to this definition, modality is reduced to discursive and epistemic. This refers to the conceptual structure of the modal sentence. However, this fact cannot be a sufficient basis for concluding that modality and irrealis can be seen as the same concept. However, there is an important difference between them. Modality is the speaker's subjective, executive or speaker's attitude towards the object, which clearly expresses its existence, while the irrealis category does not have such features.

K. Rosen states that any sentence in which the speaker clearly determines the relation of the sentence to the real through the thought he is expressing is an epistemic modal or modalized sentence.

When the modal sign is used, the speaker clearly expresses himself (his opinion, will). This self-expressive modal is considered to be specific and pre-planned because it constitutes the meaning structure. On the contrary, expression in this way does not exist in irrealis signs. They simply express the meaning expressed in the sentence and not related to the real reality. As an active expression of a sentence, it can be concluded that the speaker's speech is an event partially related to reality. Although such an approach is appreciated from a pragmatic point of view, the expression irrealis does not convey any information about the speaker. Because it is not considered subjective, indexical or executive in nature. From this point of view, the fact that irrealis is not a subjective concept in its essence is considered sufficient reason to distinguish it from modality, at least to consider the definition of modality, which combines the speaker's subjective attitude towards the topic or concept he is talking about with grammaticalization.

Another view of modality belongs to G. Hutter, who describes modality as a “real linguistic category based on fact” and not in terms of agent-oriented, discursive and epistemological qualities, or even subjectivity. Such a definition can be assessed as an attempt to eliminate the aforementioned shortcomings by reducing modality to irrealis. However, this also creates another problem. This leads us, paradoxically, to regard as modal a number of cross-linguistically related categories with irrealis markers that are difficult to recognize as modal.

In conclusion, we can agree with the views of V. Plungian. He puts forward the idea that “irrealis is closely related to modality, but not exactly the same as it.” In other words, the intersection of irrealis and modality is somewhat imperfect. It is necessary to clearly study the signs that distinguish these two concepts.

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